

Fedra Project Technical Report

Reporting Period M1 – M5

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Abstract. This report provides a comprehensive overview of the main technical results achieved in the first reporting period (months 1-5) by the project FEDRA - An institutional FAIR data lake for transparent, inclusive, and reproducible Research Assessment, funded by the CoARA Boost Cascade Funding programme, on the first call of 2024.

Keywords: Data lake · Metadata lake · FAIR principles · Open Search · Open Science · CoARA.

1 Introduction

The objective of the project FEDRA is the design of an institutional research information data lake implemented according to the FAIR principles. The starting point of the project is made by the University's Research Registry of Politecnico di Torino, which is a registry fed by multiple internal databases storing information on several research dimensions - such as projects, proposals, contracts, patents, publications and data, staff registry. A governed access to this information is seen as instrumental to develop accountable and transparent analysis, assessment, and meta-research on the University's research activities. Besides the design and implementation of a proof-of concept demonstrator of the FAIR datalake (task 1), the project includes two activities aimed at i) piloting the introduction of a dashboard focused on open science outputs other than publications (task 2) and ii) analyzing the current internal bibliometric indicators disaggregated per gender to identify any possible bias issue (task 3).

In this endeavor, the primary objectives of the technical activities carried out in the first project period have been twofold: firstly, to attain a comprehensive understanding of the technological requirements of the datalake, and secondly, to make the optimal architectural decision for the given circumstances. This process involved meticulous consideration of the FAIR principles. The collection of information was carried out on the basis of state-of-art literature, as well as through cooperation with Politecnico di Torino professionals in the divisions of IT research support services, Strategic planning and quality assurance, and Open science, and coordination with the three University's Study centres on Open science, Gender, and Strategy.

The report is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes the study on the FAIR data lake carried out in task 1. After a brief recall of the FAIR guiding principles, Subsec. 2.2 presents a review of scientific literature on data lake technology. Subsec. 2.3 describes the architecture, functionalities and technology of the existing University's Research Registry. Subsec. 2.4 introduces the preliminary architectural design and technological choices for the FEDRA data lake. A systematic comparison between the Research Registry and the FEDRA system is provided in Subsec. 2.5, aimed at outlining the improvements and integrations needed for the current Research Registry to meet the FEDRA data lake requirements. Sec. 3 presents a detailed analysis of the indicators that will be considered for the gender bias study to be done in task 3. Finally, Sec. 4 draws some preliminary conclusions and outlines next steps.

2 FAIR data lake: initial design

2.1 FAIR principles

Introduced in 2016, the FAIR principles consist in guidelines to be followed by data producers and publishers in order to guarantee findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability in all the components of the research [1], as summarized in Table1. These principles are related not only to data and its metadata but

also to algorithms, tools and workflows that led to the data itself. The FAIR Principles for research software (FAIR4RS Principles) [2], published in 2022, extend the FAIR guidelines specifically to the research software components.

Table 1. The FAIR Guiding Principles

Principle	Description
To be findable	
F1	(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
F2	Data are described with rich metadata
F3	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe
F4	(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
To be accessible	
A1	(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
A1.1	The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
A1.2	The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
A2	Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
To be interoperable	
I1	(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
I2	(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
I3	(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
To be Reusable	
R1	(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
R1.1	(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
R1.2	(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
R1.3	(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

2.2 Literature review on data lake technology

In the current era of rapid technological advancement, the volume of data being produced is increasing exponentially. Therefore, it is essential to utilise a data engineering technology capable of storing this substantial volume of data with a high level of scalability and efficiency. The data lake represents a significant and forward-thinking initiative in this field. In the current business environment, there is no universally accepted definition of a data lake, whether from a theoretical or a practical perspective. From our view, we have concluded that the most comprehensive and accurate definition is the one proposed by Sawadogo and Darmon [3]. This definition states that a data lake is a scalable storage and analysis system for data of any type, stored in their native format and used primarily by data specialists for knowledge extraction. Furthermore, a data lake has an accurate metadata catalogue, a data access and governance policy, a clear logical and physical organization and a scalable system.

From an architectural perspective, several papers differentiate between monozone architecture, pond architecture, zone architecture and lambda architecture. Each of these systems involves a data structure organised in different areas, with each area collecting a different type of data from a processing or functional point of view. From our perspective, the most promising approach is the one proposed by Ravat and Zhao [4] and reproduced in Fig. 1.

The data lake architecture is organized in two main layers. One is for data management and includes three zones - Raw data, Process, and Access - which respectively collect data in its original format, processes data, and prepares it for utilization by users. The second layer consists of the Govern zone, which is responsible for data governance, including access control and security. Notable examples of data lakes that follow the Ravat and Zhao architecture and effectively integrate the FAIR principles include the system realized by Dang, Aussenac-Gilles and Ravat [5], as well as the one proposed by Cravero, Lefiguala, Rodrigo Tralma, Sebastián Gonzalez [6].

Metadata organization plays a crucial role in data lake implementation, as well as in the context of the FAIR principles. Metadata are often categorised into three distinct types: operational, business and technical

Fig. 1. Ravat and Zaho [4] data lake architecture proposal. The data lake is divided in 4 zones: a raw data zone, in which data is kept in its original format, a process zone, in which data is manipulated, an access zone, in which data is ready to be used by a common user, and a govern zone, which is responsible of the data security and metadata organization.

[7], which highlight the type of information that the metadata carries. Other works suggest a subdivision into intra-object, inter-object and global metadata [8], depending on whether they describe a single piece of data, relations between data or a group of data. In [5], as data moves through the different zones of the data lake, metadata is created to allow the data's life cycle to be tracked. Similarly, in [6], operational, technical and business metadata are added to the raw data zone, the processing zone and the access zone, respectively. These examples imply graph-oriented modeling, since the metadata structure evolves as the data moves from the raw zone to the access zone.

2.3 Current University's Research Registry: technology and limitations

The Polito Research Registry is built on an extraction, transformation and indexing pipeline, as depicted in Fig. 2. The data, which is stored in Politecnico's Microsoft SQL servers, is first manipulated and then processed to create JSON-formatted files compatible with the Apache Solr search engine. This process is carried out periodically through a SQL ingestion queue, where each job is read and executed by a Perl application. The system also extracts data from external sources, such as the SCOPUS database, via a different SQL ingestion queue. Once the data is ready, it is indexed with Apache Solr. Apache Solr then interacts with an HTML page implemented with JavaScript and PHP, which allows users to search through a simple keyword-base search bar and filter the results. The Registry is openly accessible at Politecnico di Torino Research Database.

2.4 FEDRA data lake architecture and technological challenges

Implementing an institutional data lake involves several technological challenges:

- Advanced experience of several data engineering frameworks is needed, since big amount of data and metadata need to be ingested, manipulated and correctly exposed to the user.
- Fast and efficient communication between the different technologies involved in each zone is required, especially if you plan to create a system that is perfectly suited to your needs.

Fig. 2. POLITO Research Registry data processing pipeline overview. Data is extracted from POLITO database and from external sources. Data ingestion is orchestrated through SQL queues, whose jobs are read and executed by a Perl application. Once extracted, data is manipulated and cleaned. This data processing stage outputs JSON-formatted files compatible with Apache Solr. The latter indexes data in documents, which are organized in collections. Moreover, a web application communicates with Solr allowing user search and visualize results.

- The system must be integrated with an appropriate data security and governance framework.
- Flexible and massive storage systems are required since big amount of data is collected in various formats.
- Experimentation is required since it is a modern and not yet fully defined data engineering technology.
- The final system must be maintained over time with careful attention.

Concerning the point of massive storage requirements, it is worth outlining that the data lake envisioned in the FEDRA project encompasses a wide range of institutional data (e.g. projects, personnel, research outputs), some of which are already stored in dedicated University’s databases and repositories. Therefore, for several of these data sources, what will actually be stored in the data lake are the associated metadata, resulting in a system simpler than a full data lake, which we refer to as a *metadata lake*—a specific repository focused on ingesting, organizing, and managing metadata rather than the raw data itself. In addition, since the POLITO Research Registry already incorporates some of the key features required by the FEDRA system, it has been decided to build on this foundation and technologically improve it, in order to leverage the existing expertise of POLITO professionals. This approach retains the core objectives of the project and is coherent with the project’s temporal and resource constraints. Moreover, it can serve as a foundational layer for a future expansion toward a full data lake architecture.

The following points describe the FEDRA data lake, whose functional architecture is sketched in Fig. 3, and outline the project’s main technological challenges. It is worth noticing that a key design requirement of the FEDRA data lake is to ensure that data is easily accessible to both humans and machines, in accordance with FAIR principles. This is achieved by providing data in HTML format via the web interface and in JSON format via a dedicated API.

- A) The system ingests JSON-formatted data from the POLITO data warehouse, as well as integrating it with data from other free and open-source databases, such as Software Heritage and Open Alex, via their APIs.

Fig. 3. FEDRA Project Functional Architecture. JSON-formatted data is periodically collected by POLITO MSQL Server, integrated with data from external free and open source databases and stored in a DBMS. The database can be queried via API. The source code can be downloaded via API or open source code repositories. A web application allows common users to access data via a user-friendly HTML dashboard.

This aligns strongly with F2 (*Data are described with rich metadata*), I2 (*(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles*), I3 (*(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data*), R1 (*(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes*), R1.2 (*(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance*) FAIR principles.

- B) Data is stored in a relational database implemented with open-source tools like MySQL, SQLite or PostgreSQL and/or indexed with an open-source search engine like Apache Solr or OpenSearch. The main entities are Phd Student, Research Staff, Patent, Theses and anything that is produced in a research project, for example paper, code or dataset. This aligns strongly with F4 (*(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource*), A2 (*Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available*) and I1 (*(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation*) FAIR principles.
- C) An open, free, and universally implementable API allows expert users to query directly the database and receive the output in JSON format. This aligns strongly with A1 (*(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol*), A1.1 (*The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable*), I1 (*(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation*) FAIR principles.
- D) The entire system's source code can easily be downloaded by an open, free, and universally implementable API or by a free code repository framework such as Zenodo or GitHub. This aligns strongly with A1 (*(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol*), A1.1 (*The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable*) FAIR principles.
- E) A web application enables non-expert users to access statistics and search the database via a user-friendly dashboard. This aligns strongly with A1 (*(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol*), A1.1 (*The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable*), I1 (*(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation*).

- F) Access to the database, whether via the API or the web application, is regulated using an open-source security framework such as KeyCloak, Apache Ranger or Authlib, so that only authorised professionals can access the most sensitive data. This aligns strongly with A1.2 (*The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary*), R1.1 (*(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license*) and R1.3 (*(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards*) FAIR principles.

It is important to note that correctly matching data from POLITO databases with data from external sources is crucial in order to univocally identify each element and avoid duplicates or data with missing connections. This issue also takes into account the F1 (*(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier*), F3 (*Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe*) and I3 (*(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data*) FAIR principles. This aspect will be addressed in the second part of the project.

An overview of the main characteristics of the envisioned architecture of the FEDRA datalake and their connection to the FAIR principles is summarized in Table 2.4.

FEDRA Feature	FAIR Principles
Metadata integration through external sources	F2, I2, I3, R1, I3, R1, R1.2
Searchable indexing	F4, A2
Open APIs and protocols	A1, A1.1, I1
Security and access control	A1.2, R1.1, R1.3
Persistent identifiers	F1, F3

Table 2. Mapping of FEDRA Features to FAIR Principles

2.5 Match & Gap Analysis

As previously mentioned, the FEDRA system builds upon the existing POLITO Research Registry, which already incorporates several key features aligned with the FAIR principles. The current work focuses on technologically enhancing this foundation to realize the FEDRA data lake, thus leveraging the existing expertise and infrastructure of the University.

Based on the analysis presented in Subsec. 2.3 and 2.4, the following list highlights the similarities and differences between the POLITO Research Registry and the envisioned FEDRA data lake system:

- A) The Research Registry ingests JSON-formatted data from the POLITO data warehouse and integrates it with data coming from external sources. However, the external databases queried are not free neither open-source.
- B) Data in the Research Registry is indexed using an open-source tool, but not all required information is available. For instance, data about patents, code and software is missing.
- C) The Research Registry does not provide an open, free, and universally implementable API that allows expert users to directly query the database and receive results in JSON format.
- D) The entire Research Registry’s source code cannot be downloaded via an open, free, and universally implementable API or through free code repository frameworks such as Zenodo or GitHub.
- E) In the Research Registry, a web application enables non-expert users to access statistics and search on the database via a user-friendly dashboard.
- F) Access to the Research Registry, whether via the API or the web application, is not managed using an open-source security framework.

Still referring to the points discussed in Chapter 2.4, the following list outlines the technological improvements needed for the Research Registry to meet the FEDRA project requirements.

- A) Implementation of data ingestion process from OpenAlex (and other sources, such as Software Heritage, if time allows) and synchronization of the new data with the POLITO research outputs data.
- B) Integration of current data entities with the missing ones.
- C) Development of an open, free, and universally implementable API that allows expert users to query directly the database and receive the output in JSON format.
- D) Publication of the entire Research Registry’s source code in a free code repository platform (e.g. GitHub), or implementation of an open, free, and universally implementable API to enable its download.
- E) Including filter options in the web application, with the introduced new data attributes.
- F) Installation of an open-source security framework to manage access via the API.

The integration of free and open-source external sources, such as OpenAlex and Software Heritage, serves a dual purpose. First, it enriches the institutional data lake by providing information on research outputs not captured in internal databases, or by adding metadata to existing records (e.g., details about external authors of publications), thereby enabling more comprehensive and contextualized research assessment. Second, it supports the long-term goal of transitioning from proprietary and costly infrastructures (e.g., Scopus, WoS) to open, community-driven platforms that promote transparency, sustainability, and adherence to FAIR data principles.

3 Gender bias analysis: background data description

The Politecnico di Torino publishes a **Gender Equality Report (GER)** every three years, providing a critical analysis of key data on the academic population, disaggregated by gender.

In particular, with reference to the scope of Task 3, the data analyzed concern the scientific output of tenured academic personnel, including full professors, associate professors, and both fixed-term and permanent researchers (PO, PA, and RT). Given the availability of data and analyses from the two Gender Equality Reports published so far, a deeper analysis over a broader timespan was considered appropriate to examine how scientific output is evaluated for tenured academic staff, in order to verify whether the evaluation algorithm applied in the edition 2023 may have introduced bias.

In fact, Politecnico developed an algorithm for the assessment of scientific publications based, among other factors, on the three indicators (highly cited publications, top 10% publications, and other research outputs). These indicators, disaggregated by gender, are reported in the 2020 GER (Fig.4.17.1.B, pg. 112) and in the 2023 one (Fig. 4.14.1.A, pg. 116). The fourth column in the first figure reports also an Average Individual Contribution obtained by the algorithm by each full professor. Since the algorithm for evaluating the score was changed in between 2020 and 2023, and such score plays a role in the allocation of institutional resources to academic structures (e.g. the research departments and, in cascade, their internal research divisions), the research question was whether such change had different impact by gender. More generally, it was suggested to developing a FAIR data lake for research products such that any change in the internal procedures for their evaluation could be tested on any possible bias dimension. The 2020 edition showed a higher value of the overall score for women - consistent with their higher score across all three indicators- whereas the evaluation of the overall score in the 2023 GER was not reported in the GER, since the contemporary modifications of the algorithm did not allow for such an evaluation at the time.

In the following we illustrate the **data, metrics, and indices** used for evaluation and reported in the 2023 Gender Equality Report.

a) Data

The data used refer to the scientific output of tenured academic staff — full professors, associate professors, and both permanent and fixed-term researchers (PO, PA, RT) — over a three-year period (e.g., in the 2023 GER, the scientific output refers to the years 2020–2022, while the reference period for the products classified as HCS is 2019–2021). The following types of research outputs are considered:

- Journal Articles
- Book Chapter
- Books (only for non-bibliometric disciplines)
- Peer-reviewed conference proceedings (limited to a selected list of international conferences, as described below)

- Patents, limited to the types detailed in the following section

b) **Metrics for bibliometric fields**

- HCS: All output types included in the SCOPUS list (extracted via SciVal) called "Outputs in Top Citation Percentiles". This list, hereafter referred to as the Top 15
- Journal Articles indexed in WoS and/or Scopus: These are classified from A to D depending on the quartile of the journal within its Subject Category (WoS) or ASJC (Scopus). The quartile is determined by the journal's best position based on:
 - Impact Factor (IF) and Article Influence (AI) for WoS-JCR;
 - CiteScore (CS) and Scimago Journal Ranking (SJR) for Scopus.
- Other Outputs: Patents, book chapters, proceedings (

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2 pages), and unclassifiable articles.

Product	Score
International patents commercially exploited	2
HC Top 15% & National patents commercially exploited	1
Class A articles (1st quartile)	1
Class B articles (2nd quartile)	0.8
Class C articles (3rd quartile)	0.5
Class D articles (4th quartile or non-indexed journals)	0
Book chapters with ≥ 10 pages	0.25
International patents with spin-off agreement	2
International and national patents with spin-off agreement	1
National patents	0.5
Book chapters with < 10 pages	0
Peer-reviewed conference proceedings (> 2 pages)	0.15

Table 3. Scoring system for different research products

c) **Metrics for non-bibliometric fields**

- HCS: Includes all products in the Top 15
- Journal articles in Class A journals listed by ANVUR for the National Scientific Qualification (ASN) — product class "A".
- Journal articles in Scientific Journals listed by ANVUR for ASN (not subdivided by class) — product class B/C.
- Articles published in WoS/Scopus journals that rank higher (based on IF/AI/CS/SJR) than ANVUR-listed journals — product class A or B/C.
- Articles not on ASN lists but included in the non-bibliometric panels of the ANVUR VQR lists — product class B/C.
- Peer-reviewed articles (> 2 pages) in international conferences included in the selected list described below.
- National and international patents and patents with spin-off agreements.
- Books and book chapters.

In the 2023 GER, classification is indicated as follows:

- Top A \rightarrow articles in Q1 journals (Class A, 1st quartile)
- Top B \rightarrow articles in Q2 journals (Class B, 2nd quartile)
- Top C \rightarrow articles in Q3 journals (Class C, 3rd quartile)
- Top D \rightarrow articles in Q4 journals or non-indexed journals (Class D, 4th quartile)
- Other products \rightarrow patents, book chapters, proceedings (> 2 pages), unclassifiable articles.

Product	Score
International patents commercially exploited	2
HC Top 15% & National patents commercially exploited	1
A (journals in the “A” ASN list or 1st quartile WOS/Scopus)	1
B/C (journals in the ASN list, VQR list, or 2nd/3rd quartile WOS/Scopus)	0.65
D (journals not indexed in any list, or in 4th quartile WOS/Scopus, or without IF/AI/CS/SJR)	0
Peer-reviewed articles in international conference proceedings (>2 pages)	0.15
International patents with spin-off agreement	2
International and national patents with spin-off agreement	1
National patents	0.5

Table 4. Scoring system for research products (ASN/VQR criteria)

- d) **Ownership degree** Each product’s score is multiplied by an ownership share that accounts for the number of internal and external co-authors, defined as follows:

$$\text{Ownership degree} = \left(\frac{1}{n}\right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}}$$

where:

- n is the total number of authors.
- Internal authors count as 1.
- External authors (national or international) count as 0.7.
- If $n > 10$, the factor is fixed at 0.1.

- e) **Score**

The score assigned to each scientific output is calculated by multiplying the metric-based score by the ownership share:

$$\text{Product Score} = \text{Metric Score} \times \text{Ownership Share}$$

In the 2020 GER, all authors with an institutional ID at the university were considered “internal,” regardless of contract type or academic role. This included not only tenured staff (professors and researchers) but also collaborators, research fellows, scholarship holders, and other affiliated individuals.

In the 2023 GER, the definition of “internal author” was limited to tenured academic staff, including individuals holding a legally recognized permanent academic position, including Full Professors (PO), Associate Professors (PA), and Researchers (RT).

- f) **Indices**

As with indicators on research funding attraction capacity, the 2020 and 2023 GER include the following two indices:

- Average Individual Contribution: The ratio between the total metric score associated with a given gender/role and the number of individuals of that gender in that role (e.g., total score of female researchers divided by the number of evaluated women in that role).
- Gender Incidence: The ratio between the percentage share of the metric score associated with a gender and the gender’s percentage representation among the evaluated academic population. The analysis is conducted per academic role. For example, the incidence of female full professors is calculated as the ratio between the share of publication scores attributable to female full professors and the total score of all evaluated full professors (male and female), and the percentage of female full professors among all evaluated full professors.

In accordance with the project plan, during months M6–M12 a meta-datalake will be created to collect metadata on publications relevant for the analysis.

The change in the definition of “internal author” might have impacted the calculation of the ownership share and, consequently, the overall score attributed to each gender. By narrowing the scope to tenured academic staff in 2023, the algorithm excluded contributions from non-tenured personnel—who may disproportionately belong to one gender—thus potentially altering the gender distribution of scores. As a first step

we evaluated the score for full professors, and such effect was not noticed: the female score remains higher than the male one, consistently with other indicators, as shown in Figure 4. Average Individual Contribution values by gender and academic rank. It is important to assess though whether this redefinition introduces a structural bias at different career levels, and to evaluate its effects over a broader time span — an objective that will guide the next phase of the project.

Fig. 4. Average Individual Contribution values by gender and academic rank.

4 Conclusion

This report has presented the results of the technical activity carried out during the first reporting period (M1–M5) of the FEDRA project. The work has laid the basis for the development of an institutional FAIR data lake for analysis and assessment of the University’s research activities by conducting a thorough analysis of the existing POLITO Research Registry and identifying the technological requirements for the new system. A preliminary architectural design for the FEDRA data lake has been identified, aligned with FAIR principles, and a detailed match-and-gap analysis of the data lake with respect to the existing Research Registry has been carried out to pinpoint the improvements needed. In parallel, the project carried out a review of data and bibliometric indicators that form the basis for the analysis of the research outcomes of the academic population disaggregated by gender.

In the upcoming phases (M6–M12), the project will focus on implementing the identified technological enhancements, including the integration of new data sources (e.g., OpenAlex, Software Heritage), the development of an open and interoperable API / at least for a subset of data, and the design and, if time allows, the adoption of an open-source security framework for access management. Additionally, a subset metadata-lake of FEDRA, limited to publications only, will be developed to support a gender bias analysis on publications, particularly focusing on co-authorship patterns and the effectiveness of revised ownership metrics.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to acknowledge the colleagues Emanuele Venezia, Francesca Montagna, Mauro Paschetta, and Giorgio Santiano for useful discussions.

Author Contributions

The contributions of the authors to the FEDRA project are outlined according to the CRediT taxonomy. **Contributions to the :** **Conceptualization** – F.C., A.Mo.; **Methodology** – F.C., A.Mo., M.G. A.M.Ma, L.E., A.C.; **Software** – M.G., P.T.; **Validation** – M.G., P.T.; **Formal Analysis** – M.G., A.C, A.M.Ma, A.Mo, L.E.; **Investigation** – M.G.; **Resources** – F.C.; **Data Curation** – M.G., A.C., A.M.Ma., L.E.; **Writing** – Original Draft – M.G. (FAIR data lake study), A.C., A.M.Ma., A. Mo., L.E. (Gender bias analysis); **Writing – Review & Editing** – F.C.; all authors have read and approved the final version of this report; **Visualization** – M.G.; **Supervision** – F.C.; **Funding Acquisition** – F.C.

Funding disclaimer

The FEDRA project is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Funded within the framework of the CoARA Boost Project under grant agreement No 101131826.

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